

**GOALS AND TASKS OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT
"ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN EDUCATION"**

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The subject **"Advanced foreign experiences in education"** prepares students of higher educational institutions to effectively organize pedagogical activities. Developed countries ensure the organization of educational processes at a high level by applying the educational system and methods that are highly effective in them to the educational system of Uzbekistan. " In the course of the person-oriented training, students are taught the practical and theoretical aspects of developing their creativity, shaping the characteristics of the teacher's speech culture in his oral and written speech, evaluating and controlling student knowledge on the basis of international assessment programs. " .¹

The stability of the country's economy, its ability to compete with developed countries in all fields, in turn, depends on the personnel in the labor market. The personnel who develop the country's economy study and grow up in educational institutions. Therefore, a quality education system builds quality personnel, and quality personnel builds a developed, rich society.

In this context, investing in human capital and reforming education have become one of the priorities today. In particular, in the last two years, a number of measures aimed at increasing the authority of teachers in the society were taken, presidential schools, creative schools, and specialized schools were established in all regions of the country, and the most qualified specialists were attracted to these educational institutions. Also, the material and technical base of existing schools is being strengthened, modern schools are being built in all regions.

All in the field reforms done from raising first , of course , international experiences study , analysis _ _ to do and the results watching to go important importance occupation is enough In countries take going education _ _ of politics where level effect giving international in ratings own _ _ on the contrary finds _

Uzbekistan _ _ in the Republic developed countries to the experience relied on without higher education _ _ systematic reform make , his priority directions _ _ set get , time requirements suitable , competitive , independent thinking qualification have personnel preparation to the process main attention _ _ focus necessity there is Education _ _ process quality in terms of new to stage raise , advance _ _ _ _ education _ _ technologies apply _ _ through the rest _ _ _ of pedagogues professional competence development today's of the day current issues is one

The purpose of teaching this subject:

¹ <http://elibrary.ru>. Historical i methodological aspect formation Yazykovoy lichnosti c pedagogy .

Students of higher education institutions

advanced foreign experiences in organizing the educational process and ensuring its quality, modern approaches, advanced foreign experiences in the field of modern education and innovative technologies;

modular credit system, differential, integrative, distance education, master classes, webinar, mastering, introduction, application and creation of heuristic methods in educational practice;

improving the knowledge of the pedagogue about the development of innovative activities, identifying and analyzing problems in the development of innovative activities, as well as their knowledge about innovative educational technologies, innovative forms, methods and tools of teaching, qualities of pedagogical competence, and a creative approach to the organization of the educational process on the basis of improvement, it consists in the formation of skills and competencies by them on the creation of necessary conditions for the effective mastering of innovative approach, qualities of pedagogical competence and creative ability.

The task of science.

Science to achieve these goals:

- clarification of advanced foreign experiences in organizing the educational process and ensuring its quality, their peculiarities and areas of application;

- development of students' modular credit system, skills and competencies of effective use of foreign experiences;

- development of students' ability to effectively use advanced foreign educational technologies in the field of modern education and innovative technologies;

- organization of innovative pedagogical activities among students ;

- they have the skills of appropriate and purposeful use of educational technologies aimed at creative thinking in the effective organization of the pedagogical process: case study, project education, vitagen, scamper, design thinking, synergetic education and portfolio technologies development;

- improving students' skills in developing educational projects, forming portfolios and putting them into practice;

- development of pedagogical competence qualities in students ;

- improving the skills of a creative approach to the organization of training sessions, spiritual and educational events .

for students' knowledge, skills and competences

Within the framework of issues to be implemented in the process of mastering the subject "Foreign experiences in education":

Student:

- advanced foreign experiences in organizing the educational process and ensuring its quality;

- peculiarities of educational systems of developed countries;

- advanced foreign experiences in the field of modern education and innovative technologies: distance education, master classes, webinar classes, heuristic methods;

- innovative processes in the educational system;

- theoretical foundations of modernization of the educational system;

- Stages of innovation processes;

- Innovative activity of the teacher in improving the quality of education;

Recommendations on the organization and conduct of training

The subject "Foreign experiences in education" is conducted in the form of lectures and practical exercises. In the process of teaching science, it is envisaged to use modern methods of education, information and communication technologies: presentation and electronic didactic technologies with the help of modern computer technologies in lectures; In practical training, use technical tools, express questions, test questions, brainstorming, group thinking, working with small groups, organizing trainings, holding colloquiums, assistance and other interactive educational methods. is intended.

The role of science in higher education. By mastering science, students will acquire projective, creative and technological professional competence to master and apply foreign educational technologies . The skills of mastering, introducing and applying innovative educational technologies, qualities of pedagogical competence and creative abilities are developed.

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